

Abstract: Feed cost poses a greater challenge in broiler management as it accounts for 70-80%. Exclusive reliance on traditional diets and high cost formulated feeds alone may hinder optimal broiler production. Therefore, exploring alternative feed sources is essential to address nutritional gaps in proteins, vitamins and minerals in poultry diets. Cereal fodder hydroponics is a novel cost-effective technique for growing plants, using water or nutrient-rich solution by regulating optimum temperature and humidity for the growth of sprouts and production of highly nutritious green fodder for poultry and livestock. Including both the seed and the root is highly consumable and contains a substantial protein content of 10-17%. It takes only 8 days to grow from seed to fodder. As an alternative feed source, hydroponic fodder can be integrated into broiler diets owing to its significant benefits for broiler farmers by enhancing various aspects of poultry health and production performance. Further research studies are in the need of the hour for standardize this technology and explore its potential.

Introduction:

Poultry is a key source of animal protein and excels at converting non-human feed into nutritious food. Owing to the enormous rise in demand for animal protein, broiler meat provides a crucial and cost-effective source of animal protein, complementing other protein sources as a key component in meeting the growing demand for protein across the nation (Sultana *et al.*,2022). Feed cost poses a greater challenge in broiler management as the feed solely accounts for 70-80% of total cost of production in the Intensive system of broiler

production which is only 60–70% of economics when compared to that of layers and breeders flock. Broiler diets are made of cereal grains like maize and wheat as an energy component, along with protein sources majorly of soybean meal or groundnut cake. Increasing demand for cereals has driven up feed prices, resulting in lower net returns from broiler farming, adding to which cereals often have anti-nutritional factors that can restrict the availability of vital nutrients. As a result, exclusive reliance on traditional diets might not fully support the optimal growth and meet the desired standards for broiler carcass in terms of quality and quantity. Also, these kinds of formulated feeds pose a higher cost on production as the demand and price for cereals keep rising. Therefore, exploring alternative feed sources is essential to address nutritional gaps in proteins, vitamins and minerals in poultry diets (Baye *et al.*,2024; Atturi *et al.*,2020). Poultry nutritionists have explored various methods to produce safe and high-quality broiler meat by using alternatives to traditional antibiotics, hormones, and chemicals. Those methods include supplementation of feeds with probiotics, prebiotics, acidifiers, and different medicinal plants and herbs (Sultana *et al.*,2022). Among these natural and safe feed supplements, cereal fodder hydroponic (wheat sprouts, maize, barley etc..) stands out as a promising option for enhancing the quality and safety of broiler meat with minimal cost and higher economic returns to the farmers. For years, this feeding practice has also been employed to boost immune function, improve intestinal health, and enhance both meat quality and production performance in broiler chickens (Atturi *et al.*,2020; Al-Kanaan,2022).

Hydroponics – an Alternative to conventional feeds

Hydroponics is a cutting-edge technique for growing plants, using water or nutrient-rich solution by regulating optimum temperature and humidity for the growth of sprouts without the actual requirement of soil. This approach facilitates the quick and efficient production of highly nutritious green fodder. This method of growing plants and fodder also ensures for the production of high-nutritive feed. As an alternative feed source, hydroponic fodder can be integrated into broiler diets. (Jemimah *et al.*,2015 and Atturi *et al.*,2020). Sprouting of grains like wheat, maize, barley, sorghum and various legumes increases the biological value of protein by breaking down available proteins into amino acids and smaller peptides, enhancing lysine content and activating vital enzymes and vitamins. This process improves the nutritional profile by increasing protein quality and quantity due to loss of dry matter, essential minerals and vitamins (up-to 20 times), but this phenomenon also increases the bioavailability of certain minerals through chelation with the reduction of anti-nutritional factors in poultry feeds. For example, this technique of cereal grain production increases the bioavailability of phosphorous by inhibiting the action of phytic acid (anti-nutritional factor) by the release of phytase enzyme at the stage of sprouting. Hydroponic fodder from sprouted grains is particularly beneficial for meat animals such as poultry, rabbits, and pigs due to their lower starch and high sugar content which in turn enhances feed efficiency. Yellow maize, barley, cowpea, horse gram, wheat sprout, sun hemp, ragi, bajra, foxtail millet and jowar have been cultivated and fed successfully to the livestock and poultry as a fodder. It also offers a year-round growing method ensuring a steady and high-quality supply of animal fodder, irrespective of external weather conditions. It also promotes efficient water usage, substantial reduction in land usage when compared to other conventional methods. It takes only 8 days to grow from seed to fodder with reduction of man power and energy, whereas in case of traditional fodder it takes around 45 days to reach maturity. Hydroponic fodder, including both the seed and the root (sprout mat) is highly consumable and contains a substantial protein content of 10-17%. It provides an ideal,

nutrient-rich feed for livestock and poultry (Jemimah *et al.*,2015, Mishra,2019; Atturi *et al.*,2020; Sultana *et al.*,2022; Al-Kannan,2022; Baye *et al.*,2024).

Hydroponics – Growth and Cultivation

The process begins with drying the seeds in direct sunlight prior to washing and then storing them in a dry place. At the time of cultivation, the dried seeds are washed in a clean water which is followed by soaking the seeds in water for 20 hours of time. After soaking, the seeds are allowed to sprout in a gunny bag for the next 24 hours which will increase the weight of the seeds by 35 to 40%. Next, the sprouted seeds are placed in trays and then arranged in the machine. Each day, the trays are moved up to the next level within the machine. By the 8th day, the fodder will be fully grown and ready for harvest (Jemimah *et al.*,2015; Atturi *et al.*,2020).

Advantages of feeding Cereal Fodder Hydroponics to Broilers:

Only a handful of researches have been carried out on the adding the hydroponics fodder in the diet of broilers which include only maize, barley and wheat sprouts. It has been found that Vitamin C is essential in managing poultry, where it helps in reducing the physical and mental stresses arising due to high environmental temperatures, transportation, molting, debeaking and vaccination. Since, cereal grains are poor in or vitamin C, the process of sprouting these grains could enrich the vitamin levels as well as enhancing their biological activity (Sultana *et al.*,2022). Research studies from Sultana *et al.* (2022) stated that the pathway for the de-novo synthesis of vitamin C in the hydrophobic fodder from the precursor molecules. Though the addition of β -glucans in the livestock and poultry feed from various sources like yeast, fungi and certain cereals can boost the immune systems of birds and other animals, a high inclusion of barley hydroponic fodder can have detrimental effects on poultry performance (Schawartz and Vetvicka,2021; Al-Kanaan,2022). But, inclusion of Barley sprouts in the diets upto 10.5% significantly enhances growth performance, live body weight gain, carcass yield and net income than the inclusion of other cereal fodders (Baye *et al.*, 2024). Al-Kanaan (2022) stated

that the high inclusion level upto 15-20% hydroponic barley to broiler diets also improves carcass characteristics, blood profiles, with body weight increasing by 15-17% by the fifth week from two weeks of age (Talalay *et al.*,2020). Al-Kanaan (2022) also stated that the 10% inclusion of fresh chopped hydroponic barley fodder enhances productive performance, microbial balance and intestinal morphology, reducing broiler production costs by 9% over five weeks from two weeks of age. He also observed that the feeding of 10% hydroponic barley fodder diet to the birds of 35 days old showed lower counts of fungi, bacteria, and *E. coli* with higher levels of beneficial bacteria (*Lactobacillus sp.*). Hydroponic barley fodder also promotes beneficial bacteria while reducing harmful microorganisms also increasing the villus height and crypt depth for better nutrient absorption and utilization. Additionally, a higher count of beneficial microbes helps to suppress harmful toxins and pathogens, thereby redirecting more energy towards growth and production (Al-Kanaan,2022). Similarly, inclusion of 25% hydroponic maize fodder in the diet of broilers has reduced the cumulative feed intake and Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) value from 1.74 to 1.60 in the 6th week, which lowered the cost of feeding in broiler meat production (Atturi *et al.*,2020). Adding 50 grams of wheat sprouts per kilogram of feed enhances growth, lowers the serum cholesterol and triglycerides and also raises High-Density Lipoprotein (HDL) levels, making hydroponic wheat sprouts as a recommended addition for commercial broilers (Sultana *et al.*, 2022).

Conclusion:

Cereal fodder hydroponics is a novel cost-effective technology for feeding of poultry, livestock and fish offering a better alternative for green fodder especially for farmers with limited land and challenging conditions for traditional cultivation. It also offers several other advantages like limited water requirement than the conventional method along with reduced growth time, marginal land use and constant supply throughout the year. By using locally sourced seeds and simple equipments, the technical and economic viability of hydroponics can be further enhanced, making it as a more competitive natural nutritious alternative choice for poultry feed. Hydroponic fodder offers significant benefits for

broiler farmers by enhancing various aspects of poultry health and performance. It enhances immunity through the enriched vitamin C, balances the gut micro-biome with improvement in the intestinal morphology of birds. Additionally, it promotes better feed intake and body weight gain, while positively influencing the carcass characteristics and production rates. Moreover, hydroponic fodder helps reduce to serum cholesterol levels, lowers the feed conversion ratios (FCR) and decreases overall feed costs. These advantages on hydroponic fodder creates a valuable and cost-effective feeding option for improving the efficiency and profitability of broiler farming. Since, only few research studies have been conducted by feeding hydroponics to broiler (chickens), further research studies are the need of the hour to standardize this technology and explore its potential.

References:

- Al-Kanaan AJJ. Effects of Adding Different Levels of Hydroponic Barley Fodder on the Productive Performance and Economic Value of Broiler Chickens. Arch Razi Inst. 2022 Oct 31;77(5):1853-1864. doi.: <https://doi.org/10.22092%2FARI.2022.358131.2157>
- Atturi KM, Chakravarthy K, Guduru D. Effect of hydroponic maize fodder supplementation on production performance in broilers. Forage Res. 2020;46(1):98–100.
- Baye M., Moges F. and Andualem D. (2024). Effect of hydroponic barley fodder on growth performance, carcass yield and carcass quality of cobb 500 broilers, Heliyon, Volume 10, Issue 13, 2024, e33909, ISSN 2405-8440. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e33909>.
- Mishra R. (2019). Importance and role hydroponics feeding in livestock as source of green fodder, Agriallis- science for agriculture and allied sector, Volume 1 – Issue 5, Article Id: AL201931, Online ISSN: 2582-368X.

R. E. Jemimah , P. T. Gnanaraj, T. Muthuramalingam, T. Devi et al.,2015 - Hydroponic Green Fodder Production-TANUVAS experience, National Agricultural Development Programme (NADP).

https://rkvy.nic.in/Uploads/SucessStory/TAMILNADU/2016/2016023524Hydroponic_Final.pdf

Schwartz B, Vetvicka V. Review: β -glucans as Effective Antibiotic Alternatives in Poultry. *Molecules*. 2021 Jun 10;26(12):3560. doi: 10.3390/molecules26123560. PMID: 34200882; PMCID: PMC8230556.

Sultana, M., Das, S., Dey, B., Salam, A., Afrin, A., & Ahmed, T. (2022). Effect of Hydroponic Wheat Sprout on the Growth Performance, Carcass Characteristics, and Lipid Profiles of Broilers. *Brazilian Journal of Poultry Science*, 24(3), eRBCA-2021-1583. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1806-9061-2021-158>.

Talalay GS, Matserushka AR, Kolesnikov RO, Gvozdaryov DA, Matserushka VV. Influence of Feeding with Hydroponic Green Fodder from Barley on Meat Quality of Chicken-Broilers. *J Modern S T Equip Problem Agric*. 2020:225–34.